

Sample Name: dNMPs 400uM -P-2 50x

```

=====
Acq. Operator   : SYSTEM                      Seq. Line :    1
Sample Operator : SYSTEM
Acq. Instrument : HPLC-UV-FC                 Location  :    1
Injection Date  : 1/8/2021 11:30:07 AM      Inj       :    1
                                           Inj Volume: 50.000 µl
Method         : C:\Users\Public\Documents\ChemStation\3\Data\dNMP to dNTP yield 2021-01-08
                11-29-04\dNTP QUANTIFICATION.M (Sequence Method)
Last changed   : 12/10/2020 6:09:05 PM by SYSTEM
=====
    
```


Fraction Information

No Fractions found.

Area Percent Report

```

Sorted By      : Signal
Multiplier     : 1.0000
Dilution       : 1.0000
Do not use Multiplier & Dilution Factor with ISTDs
    
```

Signal 1: VWD1 A, Wavelength=254 nm

Peak #	RetTime [min]	Type	Width [min]	Area [mAU*s]	Height [mAU]	Area %
1	2.099	BB	0.0685	35.58702	8.14027	1.6261
2	2.221	BV	0.0390	5.84657	2.37023	0.2672
3	2.280	VB	0.0455	16.90592	5.58643	0.7725
4	2.438	BV	0.0933	17.88267	2.69827	0.8171
5	2.646	VV	0.1207	39.22580	4.69762	1.7924
6	3.052	VV	0.1113	14.69828	1.82819	0.6716

